

ISic3583

Fragment of a Latin inscription

Language

Latin

Type

unknown

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

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Autopsy

2015

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Excavated in 1971, in room 7 of the west portico of the agora

Coordinates

37.997856, 14.262463

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa

Physical Description

A single fragment of off-white marble, intact along the upper margin, broken on the other three sides (height 17.5 cm; width (at top) 10 cm; depth not recorded).

Dimensions

Height 17.5 cm

Width 10 cm

Depth unknown cm

Layout

The remains of three Latin letters in a single line are visible on the lower part of the face, with a large vacat above.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are neatly carved, with a relatively deep V section, but very limited use of serifs in what little survives.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 66 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: N/A mm

Text

1. [---]OD[---]

Apparatus

Text from photograph

Translation

Commentary

The first letter is clearly an O. Given the relative proportions, and the lack of serif to the top left of the second letter, this is a D. The remains of the upper

part of a vertical stroke are visible to the right. There is no obvious reason to associate this fragment with any of the other surviving fragments. The fragment is likely to belong to the first or second century AD.

Digital identifiers:

TM 645662

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Bibliography

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